

**Protein Coronas Coating Polymer-Stabilized Silver Nanocolloids
Attenuate Cytotoxicity with Minor Effects on Antimicrobial Performance**

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HIGHLIGHTS

- Protein adsorption is detected at the surface of polymer-stabilized silver colloids
- Amount of adsorbed proteins depends on the chemical nature of the polymeric shells
- The protein layers attenuate cytotoxicity of the silver nanoparticles
- Protein coronas does not notably influence the biocidal performance of the colloids

**Protein Coronas Coating Polymer-Stabilized Silver Nanocolloids
Attenuate Cytotoxicity with Minor Effects on Antimicrobial
Performance**

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ABSTRACT

Silver nanoparticles are versatile platforms with a variety of applications within the biomedical field. In this framework, their presence in biological media inevitably leads to the interaction with proteins thus conducting to the formation of biomolecular coronas. This feature alters the identity of the nanomaterial and may affect many biological events. These considerations motivated the investigation of protein adsorption onto the surface of polymer-stabilized AgNPs. The metallic colloids were coated by polyethyleneimine (PEI), polyvinylpyrrolidone (PVP), and poly(2-vinyl pyridine)-*b*-poly(ethylene oxide) (PEO-*b*-P2VP), and nanoparticle-protein interaction was probed by UV-vis spectroscopy, light scattering, and sodium dodecyl sulphate-polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis (SDS-PAGE). The data revealed a higher extent of protein adsorption at the surface of AgNPs@ PVP whereas PEO-*b*-P2VP coating conducted to the least amount of adsorbed proteins. The main component of the protein coronas was evidenced to be bovine serum albumin (BSA), which is indeed the protein at the highest abundance in the model biological media used. We have further robustly demonstrated reduced cytotoxicity of the silver colloids coated by biomolecular coronas as compared to the pristine counterparts. Nevertheless, the protein coatings did not notably reduce the antimicrobial performance of the polymer-stabilized AgNPs. Accordingly, although the protein-repelling property is frequently targeted towards longer *in vivo* circulation of nanoparticles, we herein underline that protein coatings, which are commonly treated as artifacts to be avoided, may indeed enhance the biological performance of nanomaterials. These findings are expected to be highly relevant in the design of polymer-stabilized metallic colloids intended to be used in healthcare.

Keywords: nano-bio interface, silver colloids, protein corona, cytotoxicity, antimicrobial properties

INTRODUCTION

Noble metal nanoparticles are versatile platforms with applications for instance as constituents of sensors,[1] and as a catalytic agent.[2] They also find a variety of applications in the biomedical field. This includes the potential use in imaging tools[3] and delivery vehicles.[4] Particularly, silver nanoparticles (AgNPs) are well documented as anti-infective agents with antibacterial,[5] antifungal[6], and antiviral[7] attributes. Due to their antiviral properties, they were also recently proposed as an additional tool for combating SARS-CoV-2 towards confronting the ongoing COVID-19 pandemic.[8,9] The anti-infective properties of AgNPs are proposed to be related to the continuous release of silver ions[10] combined with the toxicity of the AgNPs themselves.[11] Indeed, the stabilizing agent notably influences the final performance of silver colloids[12] and on top of that, the biomedical application of nanoparticles frequently relies on their presence in the biological milieu. In such a scenario, they interact with a variety of available biomacromolecules, inevitably leading to the formation of so-called biomolecular coronas.[13–18] The protein coating alters the identity of the nanomaterial which may remarkably affect many biological events including, for instance, hemolytic activity,[19] cytotoxicity and immune response,[20,21] biodistribution,[22,23] targeting capability,[20,24] cellular uptake[25] and intracellular trafficking.[26] Accordingly, investigations regarding the interaction of colloidal silver with proteins are of due relevance to understand the biological effects of biomolecular coronas, as well as the fate and behavior of nanomaterials whenever in contact with living systems.

The nanoparticle-protein interaction is typically governed by intermolecular forces driven interfacial phenomena. This may include van der Waals, hydrogen bonding, electrostatic and hydrophobic effects.[27] The strength of interaction determines the

formation, chemical nature, binding affinity and binding ratio of adsorbed proteins. The novel biological fingerprint is linked to the synthetic features of the assemblies (size, shape, chemical nature of the stabilizer, surface charge, surface curvature, etc.) [28] as well as to the characteristics of the environment. [29] Truly, the presence of protein layers enveloping nanomaterials is currently understood to be paradoxical. In one hand, biomolecular coronas are undesirable since they can reduce the targeting capability of nanomaterials. [24,30] On the other hand, protein coatings can reduce cytotoxicity and enhance stability of nanomaterials, such as for instance demonstrated for silver nanoparticles exposed to serum rich medium. [31] The biological consequences of the protein corona deeply rely on the surface chemistry of nanomaterials and comparative analysis concerning different coatings is not fully understood, therefore remaining currently unknown to a high extent.

Taking into account the above-mentioned considerations, we have investigated the behavior of polymer-capped AgNPs upon contact with FBS (fetal bovine serum) with regard to the structural features and biological consequences of self-developed protein coronas. The protein adsorption onto the surface of AgNPs stabilized by PEI (polyethylenimine), PVP (polyvinylpyrrolidone) and PEO-*b*-P2VP (poly(ethylene oxide)-*b*-poly(2-vinyl pyridine)) was investigated since such polymers are commonly employed in surface passivation. The formation of biomolecular coronas around the polymer-stabilized assemblies was robustly confirmed by dynamic (DLS) and electrophoretic (ELS) light scattering, besides UV-vis spectroscopy. Respectively, increased size, changes in surface charge and red-shift on the SPR band suggested protein adsorption onto the surface of the AgNPs with the extent of coating dependent on the chemical nature of the polymeric shell. The SDS-PAGE data further revealed serum albumin as the most abundant component of the protein coronas. Subsequently, the

protein-coated nano-sized silver colloids were evaluated with regard to cytotoxicity and antimicrobial performance. The protein coatings notably reduce cytotoxicity of the nanomaterials to mammalian cells nevertheless, they do not reduce significantly the antimicrobial performance. We judge that these findings are highly relevant towards the rational design of polymer-stabilized nanoparticles for biomedical applications.

EXPERIMENTAL

Chemicals

Silver nitrate (AgNO_3), sodium borohydride (NaBH_4), PEI (branched polyethylenimine) and PVP (polyvinylpyrrolidone) were all purchased from Sigma-Aldrich whereas PEO-*b*-P2VP (poly(ethylene oxide)-*b*-poly(2-vinyl pyridine)) was purchased from Polymer Source Inc. The molecular characteristics of the polymer chains are respectively $M_n = 25000 \text{ g}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$, $M_w/M_n = 2.5$ for PEI, $M_n = 40000 \text{ g}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$, $M_w/M_n = 2.0$ for PVP and $M_n = 21000\text{-}b\text{-}13500 \text{ g}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$, $M_w/M_n = 1.1$ for PEO-*b*-P2VP. The water was previously pretreated with Milli-Q[®] Plus System (Millipore Corporation). Sabouraud dextrose agar and Mueller-Hinton (MH) agar plates were purchased from LabMediaServis Ltd. (Jaroměř, Czech Republic). MH broth base was purchased from Becton Dickinson Czechia Ltd. (Prague, Czech Republic). Heat-inactivated fetal bovine serum was purchased from Life Technologies Ltd. (Prague, Czech Republic). Components for both the malt extract broth (malt extract $17 \text{ g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$, peptone $3 \text{ g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$) and malt extract agar (malt extract $30 \text{ g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$, peptone $5 \text{ g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$, agar $15 \text{ g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$) were supplied by Carl Roth GmbH & Co. KG (Karlsruhe, Germany).

Manufacturing of the Polymer-Stabilized AgNPs

The manufacturing of the polymer-stabilized AgNPs was conducted similarly to previously reported procedures.[32] Stock solutions of sodium borohydride (NaBH_4), silver nitrate (AgNO_3), and of the polymer chains were initially prepared. Aliquots of the AgNO_3 and polymer solutions were firstly mixed at $\text{AgNO}_3/\text{polymer} = 6.8$ weight ratio and, subsequently, aliquots of the stock NaBH_4 solution were added dropwise under vigorously stirring until complete addition, and further stirred gently for 1 h. The formation of AgNPs was noticed by the appearance of a characteristic pale-yellow color. Remaining reactants were further removed by using standard dialysis protocols against pure water for at least 24 hs. The nanoparticle quantification (in ppm) has been performed as described elsewhere.[12]

Protein Adsorption in Serum Environment

The polymer-stabilized AgNPs (1.0 ppm) were incubated in diluted FBS for 1 h at 37 °C under orbital shaking at 250 rpm. Dynamic lights scattering (DLS), electrophoretic light scattering (ELS) and UV-vis spectroscopy were monitored after incubation of the silver colloids in FBS 1 % v/v to avoid notable interference of the biological media in the signals (discussed hereafter). The other experimental protocols were conducted using diluted FBS 10% v/v unless otherwise noticed.

Isolation of the Hard Protein Coronas

The first step of this protocol consisted of mixing the nanomaterial (1.0 ppm) with the biological medium (incubation) corresponding to FBS 10% v/v (1h, 37 °C). Subsequently, the isolation was induced by loading the samples into a sucrose cushion solution (0.5 mL; 0.7 mol.L⁻¹) and centrifuging to separate nanoparticle-protein

complexes from weakly bound and unbound proteins (30 min; 20.000 g; 4° C). The pellets were further washed with cold PBS (three washing steps) before the final resuspension. The details of the employed protocol are described in the literature.[33,34]

Methods of Characterization

Dynamic Light Scattering (DLS): DLS measurements were performed using an ALV/CGS-3 compact goniometer system. The autocorrelation functions were based on 3 independent runs of 120 s counting time. The data were collected and further averaged by using the ALV Correlator Control software. The correlation functions were analysed using the Cumulant method applied to the autocorrelation functions measured at 90° and the hydrodynamic radius (R_H) of the nanoparticles was determined by using the Stokes-Einstein equation with diffusion coefficient $D = \tau^{-1}q^{-2}$:

$$R_H = \frac{k_B T q^2}{6\pi\eta} \tau \quad (1)$$

k_B is the Boltzmann constant, T is the absolute temperature, q is the scattering vector, η is the viscosity of the solvent and τ is the mean relaxation time.

Electrophoretic Light Scattering (ELS): ELS measurements were used to determine the average zeta potential (ζ) of the polymer-stabilized silver colloids. The values were collected using a Zetasizer Nano-ZS ZEN3600 instrument (Malvern Instruments, UK). This instrument measures the electrophoretic mobility (U_E) and converts the value to ζ -potential (mV) through Henry's equation:

$$U_E = \frac{2 \varepsilon \zeta f(ka)}{3 \eta} \quad (2)$$

where ϵ is the dielectric constant of the medium, η is its viscosity and $f(ka)$ is the Henry's function calculated through the Smoluchowski approximation with $f(ka) = 1.5$.

UV-Vis Spectroscopy: UV-vis data were acquired by using a Varian Cary 50 spectrometer. The spectral resolution for wavelength scanning was 1.0 nm. The measurements were performed by using a quartz cell with optical path length of 1.0 mm.

Sodium Dodecyl Sulphate-Polyacrylamide Gel Electrophoresis (SDS-PAGE): The isolation method (centrifugation) previously described was followed by the elution of the nanoparticle-protein complexes *via* the addition of 0.1 mL sample buffer (62.5 mM Tris-HCl (pH 6.8), 2% (*m/v*) SDS, 1% glycerol, 0.04 mol.L⁻¹ dithiothreitol (DTT), and 0.01% (*m/v*) bromophenol blue). The samples were then incubated for 5 min at 95 °C to induce protein denaturation, then cooled to room temperature and further loaded into a stacking gel with 12% polyacrylamide subjected to electrophoresis at 125 V for about 2 hs. The gels were colored by coomassie blue staining using straightforward protocols. The images were captured using a chemiDocTM XRS image system (Bio-Rad) and their densitometries were analyzed using the ImageJ software. The protein identification was performed by direct comparison using a reference polyacrylamide gel of a single protein solution (bovine serum albumin).

Evaluation of Cell Toxicity

Cell Culture: MRC-5 fibroblasts (donated by Princeton University, USA) and HeLa (donated by Universidade Federal do Rio de Janeiro, Brazil) cells were cultured in Gibco Roswell Park Memorial Institute (RPMI) 1640 medium purchased from Life

Technologies and supplemented with 10% fetal bovine serum (FBS), 100 U.mL⁻¹ penicillin and 100 µg.mL⁻¹ streptomycin at 37 °C under CO₂ atmosphere.

MTT Assay: The viability of cells in contact with either pristine nanoparticles or the nanoparticle-protein complexes (i.e., nanoparticles previously incubated in the FBS environment) was evaluated by first seeding the respective cell lines into 96-well plates at a density of 2×10^4 cells/well and allowing them to grow for 24 hs. Subsequently, the cells were treated with fresh FBS-free RPMI 1640 and varying concentrations of the pristine nanoparticles or nanoparticle-protein complexes and incubated for 24 hs at 37 °C. Then, after washing the plates with phosphate-buffered saline (PBS), 200 µL of 0.1 mg.mL⁻¹ 3-(4,5-dimethylthiazol-2-yl)-2,5-diphenyltetrazolium bromide reagent was added to each well and the plate was incubated for 4 hs at 37 °C under CO₂ atmosphere. The formazan crystals generated by the living cells were then dissolved in 200 µL of dimethyl sulfoxide and the absorbance of the solutions at 570 nm was measured using a Synergy microplate reader. Untreated cells were used as a control to compute the percentage of cell viability. According to ISO 10993–5, a reduction in cell viability by more than 30% is considered a cytotoxic effect.

Evaluation of Antimicrobial Activity

Bacteria Strains: *Escherichia coli* (CCM 3954) and *Staphylococcus aureus* subsp. *aureus* (CCM 4223) were grown on chocolate blood agar at 37 °C for 18–24 hs. *Candida albicans* (CCM 8261) was grown on Sabouraud dextrose agar at 35 °C for 24 hs.

Agar Diffusion Assay: The agar diffusion assays were carried by firstly immersing a sterilized cotton swab in a culture suspension (0.5 McFarland units) and spread either on

MH agar or malt extract agar. The cultivation medium was supplemented with 10 % v/v FBS whenever noticed. Subsequently, a hole (10 mm in diameter) was produced by a cork borer and 100 μ L of the polymer-stabilized AgNPs (20 ppm) were added. The cultures were left incubated for 18–24 hs as appropriate and then the inhibition zones around the holes were measured. The experiments were carried out in triplicate.

Broth Microdilution Assay: The broth microdilution assay was used to estimate the minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) and minimum bactericidal concentration (MBC). The samples were serially diluted two-fold using sterile water in a round-bottom 96-well plate. Subsequently, inoculated double-concentrated Mueller–Hinton broth (bacteria, final inoculum 1×10^5 CFU) or malt extract broth (*C. albicans*, final inoculum 1×10^5 CFU) either with or without FBS (10 % v/v) were added to the serially diluted AgNPs (concentration ranging from 5 to 0.005 ppm) and the plates were left incubated. MIC values were determined as the lowest concentration of nanoparticles that inhibited visible bacterial growth (i.e., no turbidity observed). After MIC determination, aliquots of 10 μ L from wells with no bacteria growth were incubated on chocolate blood agar or Sabouraud dextrose agar as appropriate. The MBC endpoint was defined as the lowest concentration of the nanoparticles that killed 100% of the initial bacterial population (i.e., no colony occurred).

Effect of Concentration on Microbial Growth: In order to assess the influence of nanoparticle concentration on microbial growth, optical density at 600 nm was measured using a Synergy H1 Hybrid Reader instrument (Biotek, Winooski, USA). The percent growth was calculated as:

$$\% \text{ growth} = \frac{A_{\text{sample}} - A_{\text{broth}}}{A_{\text{control}} - A_{\text{broth}}} \times 100 \quad (3)$$

where A_{sample} is the absorbance of each suspension treated with AgNPs, A_{broth} is the absorbance of sterile broth and A_{control} is the absorbance of the untreated control. All the data were acquired in triplicate.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Structural Features of the Polymer-Stabilized AgNPs in the Biological Environment

The serum environment contains a notably high number of different proteins in different amounts. The fetal bovine serum (FBS) was used as the model biological environment. It contains a variety of proteins where the globular protein bovine serum albumin (BSA) is the major component. FBS is to some extent similar to the plasma media nevertheless, with lower antibody and higher growth factor levels. The behavior of the polymer-stabilized AgNPs in such a milieu was preceded by the characterization of the milieu itself. The experimental data (not shown for brevity) highlighted relatively high UV-vis absorption of the biological medium when the FBS concentration is 10% v/v or higher. The maximum absorption at $\lambda_{\text{max}} \sim 400$ nm is particularly relevant due to the absorption of the produced AgNPs at the same spectral range. Nevertheless, the experimental data underscore that the maximum absorption is notably low when the FBS concentration is below 5% v/v. In such conditions, maximum absorption always below 0.1 has been monitored. Taking into account this previous data, the light scattering and UV-vis spectroscopy analyses were performed at FBS concentration equal to 1% v/v in order to minimize its influence in the acquired set of data. The UV-vis profiles of the polymer-stabilized AgNPs in aqueous media and in the presence of FBS 1% v/v are provided in Figure 1 (left) according to the legends.

Figure 1. UV-vis profiles of the polymer-stabilized AgNPs in aqueous media and in the presence of FBS 1% v/v according to the labels (left); Respective distributions of R_H determined by dynamic light scattering (right).

Taking into account the UV-vis profiles for diluted FBS, the UV-vis profiles and respective changes reported in Figure 1 can only be assigned to structural changes in the AgNPs as caused by the protein environment. The values of λ_{\max} are reported in Table 1.

This parameter is known to be dependent on the particle size and chemical nature of the stabilizing shell.[35] Accordingly, the differences monitored are linked to the different surface chemistry in the presence and absence of biomolecular coronas. Additionally, changes in the size of the assemblies certainly impact the behavior. This assumption is based on the determined values of hydrodynamic radius which are also provided in Table 1. The dimensions are indeed remarkably influenced by the presence of the protein milieu.

Table 1. Structural parameters (R_H , λ_{max} and ζ) of the manufactured polymer-stabilized AgNPs as measured in FBS-free and 1% v/v FBS environment.

Sample	R_H (nm)		λ_{max} (nm)		ζ (mV)	
	FBS-free	FBS 1% v/v	FBS-free	FBS 1% v/v	FBS-free	FBS 1% v/v
AgNPs@PEI	30.0	79.8	392.0	411.1	+ 13.0	- 18.9
AgNPs@PVP	34.4	66.7	399.0	460.8	- 12.7	- 20.0
AgNPs@PEO- <i>b</i> -P2VP	31.1	40.3	419.9	426.0	+ 15.6	- 9.4

The red shift in the UV-vis data is more remarkable for AgNPs stabilized by PEI and PVP, whereas the shift is less noticeable for silver colloids stabilized by PEO-*b*-P2PV. The formation of protein layers is also suggested by the changes in the distributions of sizes reported in Figure 1 (right) and the respective average values of R_H in the presence and in FBS-free environment given in Table 1. Indeed, regardless of the stabilizer, the average dimension is shifted towards the right in the protein environment, pointing out accordingly increased size of the scattering objects. The negative values of ζ -potential after the incubation in the protein environment additionally support the presence of protein layers enveloping the colloidal material. Therefore, the combination of UV-vis, DLS and ELS data confirm the appearance of protein coronas around the whole set of polymer-stabilized silver colloids. The stabilization provided by PEO-*b*-P2VP seems to

overall conduct to protein adsorption to a lesser extent. This is suggested by the less pronounced difference in R_H for FBS-free and FBS environment than observed for PEI- and PVP-stabilized AgNPs. The behavior is probably linked to the protein-repelling attributes of PEO chains. Indeed, $M_{w(\text{PEO})} \sim 5000 \text{ g.mol}^{-1}$ was evidenced to provide enhanced colloidal stabilization to silica nanoparticles with almost no interaction with BSA.[36] In the current case, the PEO chains are actually notably longer ($\sim 21000 \text{ g.mol}^{-1}$). On the other hand, the size of the AgNPs stabilized by PVP and PEI increases remarkably ($\sim 30\text{-}50 \text{ nm}$) in agreement with the shift in λ_{max} towards the right-hand side. Taking into account such notable increments, protein-induced aggregation cannot be ruled out, particularly for AgNPs@PEI as suggested by the shoulder in the UV-vis spectrum at approximately 530 nm with a significant broadening of the LSPR band. Nevertheless, the monitored sizes can also be assigned to the presence of notably thick protein coronas. The monitored dimensions may account for the thickness of an inner protein shell (hard corona) surrounded by an outer shell (soft corona). The hard corona embraces proteins irreversibly bound to the surface of the polymer-stabilized assemblies whereas the soft corona is a dynamic environment containing weakly bound proteins with a high exchange rate. The possible presence of notably thick protein coronas is indeed in agreement with the current literature as evidenced by us[37] and by others[38] using different analytical techniques. In summary, the experimental data robustly confirm the presence of the protein layers surrounding the assemblies, and the extent of adsorption depends on the chemical nature of the polymeric shells.

Composition of the Hard Protein Coronas

The incubation of the silver colloids into the protein environment has been preceded by the compositional analysis of the biomolecular coronas using the resources of SDS-

PAGE. The analyses of the hard corona proteins were conducted based on recommended protocols of centrifugation and washing as described in the experimental section, and the SDS-PAGE data are provided in Figure 2.

Figure 2. (Left) Compositional analysis of the hard protein coronas around the polymer-stabilized AgNPs as visualized by Coomassie stained SDS-PAGE after the incubation in FBS 10% v/v; (Right) Respective abundance of the main protein (BSA) found at the surface of the nanoparticles normalized by the average surface area of each AgNPs (the maximum amount was set to 1).

The SDS-PAGE data clearly evidence the presence of a strong band at $M_w \sim 66$ kDa which is likely related to BSA, highly abundant in FBS. Indeed, BSA has been identified in other studies using proteomic analyses.[39,40] The protein is negatively charged at pH 7.4 (isoelectric point ~ 4.7)[41] nevertheless, the adsorption event takes place also on top of negatively charged surfaces evidencing that electrostatic repulsions are not sufficient to suppress the presence of this biomacromolecule at the surface of the polymer-stabilized AgNPs. The SDS-PAGE data also evidence weaker signal for colloidal silver stabilized by PEO-*b*-P2VP, therefore pointing out different abundancies. This is quantitatively confirmed by the gel band densitometry data provided in Figure 2 (right). The values were normalized by the total surface of the nanoparticles taking into account the monitored values of R_H (the highest value was set to 1.0 for comparison purposes). The experimental data indicate that serum albumin is bound at higher amounts at the surface of AgNPs@PVP and it progressively reduces for AgNPs@PEI and AgNPs@PEO-*b*-P2VP. This behavior is in fairly good agreement with the previously reported UV-vis and light scattering data. Overall, the combination of DLS, UV-vis, ELS and SDS-PAGE then confirms the protein adsorption onto the surface of the polymer-stabilized assemblies with higher amounts monitored for AgNPs@PVP and lower amounts for the metallic material coated by PEO-*b*-P2VP.

Evaluation of Cell Toxicity

The viability of cells upon contact with protein-coated polymer-stabilized AgNPs was evaluated in comparison with the pristine counterparts (not incubated in serum-containing medium). The data are given in Figure 3 for healthy (fibroblasts MRC-5) and cancer (HeLa) cell lines according to the y-axis labels. The cells were incubated with polymer-stabilized AgNPs or polymer-stabilized AgNPs previously incubated in 10% v/v

FBS at the same mass concentration of nanoparticles. The investigations were conducted based on the ISO 10993–5:2009.

Figure 3. Viability of MRC-5 (A) and HeLa (B) cells in contact with protein corona-containing (FBS) and bare polymer-stabilized AgNPs as a function of the mass concentration of AgNPs. The horizontal lines indicate cell viability levels where the data above are considered noncytotoxic and below cytotoxic. The results indicate mean values \pm SD.

The data clearly highlight the benefits of the protein coronas regarding the viability of mammalian cells. The cell viability data for polymer-stabilized AgNPs previously incubated with FBS 10% *v/v* are depicted in the right side (dashed bars)

whereas the analogous data for pristine polymer-stabilized AgNPs are given in the left (opened bars) according to the legend. The data provided in Figure 3 underline that regardless of the previous incubation in 10% *v/v* FBS, the PEI-stabilized nanoparticles (AgNPs@PEI) are considerably less toxic to either MRC-5 or HeLa cells (in the concentration range probed, cytotoxicity is evidenced only at 32 ppm for HeLa cells). This behavior is indeed not expected at a glance if one takes into account the fairly well-known cytotoxicity of polycations, silver colloids and silver ions. Nevertheless, it has been previously observed by us.[12] Presumably, intense intermolecular forces (electrostatic, hydrophobic, van der Waals interactions or complexation between PEI and silver) can, at least to some extent, weaken the ability of PEI chains and silver to promote cell damage. In such way, the viability of cells in the presence of AgNPs@PEI is not considerably affected by the formation of a protein corona because the hybrid material is in general not cytotoxic. Nevertheless, at 32 ppm the protein coating notably reduces cell damage. The silver colloids stabilized by PEO-*b*-PV2P and PVP demonstrated relatively high levels of cytotoxicity before incubation in the protein medium and, therefore, the beneficial effect of protein coronas is more evident. The experimental data reported in the right side of Figure 3 (A-B) evidence values of cell viability always above 70% after the incubation in FBS medium (within experimental errors) for MRC-5 cells in the whole concentration range, and up to the concentration of 12.8 ppm for HeLa cells. Truly, the MRC-5 cell line is overall more resistant to the presence of the AgNPs compared to HeLa. Additionally, one can also notice that AgNPs@PEO-*b*-P2VP are more cytotoxic than AgNPs@PVP as clearly evidence for MRC-5 cells. Regardless of the polymer coating, the cell viability notably increases after the incubation in FBS highlighting then the beneficial effect of the protein coronas enveloping AgNPs. Values of HeLa cell viability smaller than 70% have been determined only for the highest concentration evaluated (32

ppm) where the silver colloids are cytotoxic even at the presence of a protein corona. The discrepancies comparing both cell lines are possibly linked to morphological differences and cell metabolism. Tumor cells are typically more irregular, and cell growth is faster, which may contribute to greater permeation of nanoparticles, thus inducing enhanced toxicity. Nevertheless, the experimental data robustly confirm the actual benefit of the protein coronas. For instance, the viability of MRC-5 cells in contact with AgNPs@PEO-*b*-P2VP is below 70% already at $c = 6.4$ ppm whereas in the presence of a protein corona the cell viability is in the range of approximately 70% even in contact with 32 ppm (approximately 5 times higher). The quantitative differences are also similar for HeLa cells. This result is to some extent intriguing since BSA is known to enhance the AgNPs dissolution kinetic.[42–44] Nevertheless, although silver ions are an important component in silver toxicity to cells, released Ag^+ were demonstrated to be trapped within the protein corona in serum-containing cell culture media, thereby resulting in decreased toxicity of Ag NPs.[45] This possibly explains the herein evidenced beneficial effect of the protein coronas.

Evaluation of Antimicrobial Activity

We have further evaluated the antimicrobial activity of the polymer-stabilized silver colloids before and after the formation of protein coronas. The experiments were therefore carried before and after the incubation of the polymer-stabilized AgNPs in 10% *v/v* fetal bovine serum (FBS) used as protein source. The evaluations have been firstly conducted *via* the agar diffusion assay which is based on the measurement of an inhibition zone that occurs due to a compound diffusion, allowing for semi-quantitative assessment of antimicrobial properties of different materials. A Mueller-Hinton agar was used for the cultivation of *E. coli* (Gram-negative) and *S. aureus* (Gram-positive) bacterial strains

whereas malt extract agar supplemented with glucose was used for *C. albicans*. The agar diffusion assay data are reported in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Agar diffusion assay data according to the legends (FBS refers to the presence of protein corona; NZ refers to no inhibition zone).

The whole set of polymer-stabilized AgNPs revealed antibacterial activity against *S. aureus* and *E. coli* although the inhibition zone diameters are gently reduced when agar was supplemented with 10% *v/v* FBS. On the other hand, *C. albicans* was found to be resistant to the presence of the polymer-stabilized AgNPs. The fairly thin inhibition zones monitored would make more quantitative interpretations inaccurate and therefore, we have further performed a broth microdilution assay. The experimental data are provided in Table 2.

Table 2. Broth microdilution assay data (in ppm).

Sample	<i>S. aureus</i>		<i>E. coli</i>		<i>C. albicans</i>	
	MIC	MBC	MIC	MBC	MIC	MBC
AgNPs@PVP	5	> 5	1.25 - 2.5	1.25 - 2.5	> 5	> 5
AgNPs@PVP (FBS)	> 5	> 5	2.5 - 5	5	> 5	> 5
AgNPs@PEI	≥ 5	> 5	1.25 - 2.5	2.5	2.5 - 5	5
AgNPs@PEI (FBS)	≥ 5	> 5	1.25 - 2.5	≥ 5	> 5	> 5
AgNPs@PEO- <i>b</i> -P2VP	0.625	2.5	0.31 - 0.625	2.5 - 5	> 5	> 5
AgNPs@PEO- <i>b</i> -P2VP (FBS)	2.5	2.5 - 5	0.625 - 1.25	1.25	> 5	> 5

The experiments were similarly carried out without or with FBS (10% v/v in the cultivation medium) used as the protein source. The broth microdilution assay provided the values (ppm) of the minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) and the minimum bactericidal concentration (MBC). The *C. albicans* was found to be resistant regardless of the presence of any polymer-stabilized AgNPs in agreement with the previously reported agar diffusion assay.

The microdilution assay allows for quantitative characterization of the antimicrobial properties and the results reported in Table 2 evidence particularly the sensitiveness of *E. coli* and higher resistance of *S. aureus* and *C. albicans*, thereby resulting in the reduced influence of protein coronas for the last two microorganisms. The presence of protein coronas induced a reduction in the values of both microbiostatic (estimated as MIC) and microbiocidal (estimated as MBC) properties of the nanomaterials highlighting the effect of the protein corona against *E. coli*. Nevertheless, the reduction is not remarkably pronounced.

Complementarily, the microbial growth was also assessed by optical density measurements as a function of AgNPs concentration and the experimental results are provided in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Effect of AgNPs concentration on the microbial growth (%) of *S. aureus* (A), *E. coli* (B) and *C. albicans* (C) - FBS refers to the presence of a protein corona.

The data reported in Figure 5 underline that the presence of blood proteins, which are known to cover the whole set of polymer-stabilized AgNPs, influences to some extent the microbiostatic and microbicidal properties of the silver colloids. This is also linked to the chemical nature of the polymer-stabilizing shells and the particularities of the living

systems. For instance, one can notice that the effectiveness of AgNPs@PVP is reduced to higher extent compared to AgNPs@PEO-*b*-P2VP. Nevertheless, the data reported in Figure 5 highlights that the antimicrobial effect is only marginally influenced by the presence of a protein corona. This is clearly evidenced for AgNPs@PEO-*b*-P2VP regardless the bacteria strain. Indeed, we have previously identified that that the stabilization by using PEO-*b*-P2VP conducted to the least amount of adsorbed proteins. Conversely, the stabilization by using PVP conducted to the highest amount which is possibly connected to the observed differences in biocidal performance. Although the extent to which nanoparticle's features influence biological events remains debatable,[46–48] this behavior may suggest their prime effect taking into account that silver ions may remain trapped in protein coronas.[45] High amounts of adsorbed protein may then attenuate the antimicrobial performance of the silver nanoparticles. Nevertheless, this hypothesis remains a point for further and deeper investigations.

CONCLUSIONS

We demonstrated the protein adsorption onto the surface of polymer-stabilized AgNPs by UV-vis, light scattering and SDS-PAGE data. The empirical data highlight higher protein adsorption onto the surface of AgNPs@PVP whereas the stabilization provided by PEO-*b*-P2VP conducted to the least amount of adsorbed proteins. The main component of the protein coronas was evidenced to be bovine serum albumin (BSA) which is indeed the protein at the highest abundancy in the protein source. Subsequently, biological consequences of the self-developed protein coronas have been assessed. The cytotoxicity of the silver colloids coated by the biomolecular coronas is remarkably attenuated which is accordingly considered a beneficial effect. The protein coronas nevertheless only gently reduce the antimicrobial performance of the polymer-stabilized

AgNPs. The tiny influence of the surface chemistry in the phenomenon underlines the possible key effect of silver ions (Ag^+) rather than the nanoparticles themselves. These main findings (namely, attenuated cytotoxicity with balanced effect in the biocidal performance) are expected to be highly relevant in the design of polymer-stabilized metallic colloids intended to be used in the biomedical field.

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